

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Alcohols by Ceric Ammonium Nitrate

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The main product of the oxidation of secondary alcohol by ceric ammonium nitrate is the corresponding ketone. The reaction is of first-order with respect to the oxidant but exhibit a Michaelis-Menten type kinetics with respect to the alcohol. The formation constants of the alcohol-Ce^{IV} complex and its thermodynamic parameters have been calculated. The rate of decomposition of the complex and the activation parameters have also been evaluated. The rates of decomposition of the complex correlate with Taft's σ^* values with a low negative reaction constant. The oxidation induced polymerisation of acrylonitrile. The retardation of rate with increasing acidity has been explained on the formation of kinetically inactive protonated alcohol. The protonated constants for the various alcohol have been calculated. The presence of a small primary kinetic isotope effect, $k_H/k_D = 2.3$, confirms that the rate-determining step involves a C—H bond rupture in a non-symmetrical transition state.

THE oxidation of alcohols by cerium(IV) has received considerable attention¹. It is now known that an intermediate complex is kinetically significant in the reactions of cerium(IV) perchlorate² and ceric ammonium nitrate (CAN)³ but is not so in the reactions of cerium(IV) sulphate⁴. There are conflicting reports^{3,5} about the effect of acidity on the rate of oxidation by CAN. Further, the effect of structure on the formation of the intermediate complex and its decomposition has not received due attention. The present investigation was undertaken to study primarily the effect of structural variation in the alcohol molecule and the effect of acidity.

Experimental

Alcohols were commercial products. They were dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and then fractionally distilled. Propan-2-ol- α -d was prepared⁶ by the reduction of acetone with sodium and D₂O. CAN (A.R. grade, AEC, Bombay) was used as such. Ferriin indicator was prepared by dissolving *o*-phenanthroline (E. Merck) (1.85 g) and ferrous sulphate crystals (0.695 g) in water (100 ml). All other chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade. Double-distilled water was used for making solutions.

Product analysis: The product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions, *i.e.* with an excess of the substrate over the oxidant.

In a typical experiment, propan-2-ol (3.0 g, 0.05 mol) and CAN (5.5 g, 0.01 mol) were made upto 100 ml in the presence of sufficient nitric acid to make it 1.0 M in the mineral acid. The reaction mixture was kept in the dark for ~ 12 h to ensure

completion of the reaction. It was treated overnight with an excess (300 ml) of a saturated solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in 2 N HCl. The precipitated 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (DNP) was filtered off, dried, weighed, recrystallised from ethanol and weighed again. Its identity was established by m.p. (128°) and m.m.p. with an authentic sample of DNP of acetone. The yields of DNP before and after recrystallisation were 2.10 g (88%) and 1.91 g, (80%), respectively.

The other alcohols also yielded DNP of the corresponding ketones in 73-86% yields after recrystallisation.

Stoichiometry: The stoichiometry was determined by treating the alcohol with an excess of cerium(IV).

In a typical experiment propan-2-ol (0.6 g, 0.01 mol) and CAN (27.4 g, 0.05 mol) were made upto 100 ml in 1M nitric acid and allowed to stand for ~ 12 h in the dark. The residual cerium(IV) was determined by adding a known excess of ferrous sulphate solution. The excess of ion(II) was back titrated against standardised cerium(IV) sulphate solution, using ferriin as an indicator. Similar experiments with the various alcohols indicated 1 : 2 stoichiometry.

Kinetic measurements: The reactions were arranged under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping an excess of the alcohol ($\times 10$ or more) over cerium(IV). The reactions were carried out in a flask blackened outside to prevent photochemical reaction. The reactions were followed by quenching aliquots, withdrawn at suitable intervals of time, in a slight excess of ferrous sulphate solution. The residual iron(II) was determined by titration against

standardised cerium(IV) sulphate solution using ferroin as an indicator. The pseudo-first order rate constants, k_1 , were determined from linear ($r > 0.98$) plots of $\log [Ce^{4+}]$ against time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rates are reproducible within $\pm 4\%$.

Results and Discussion

The rate data were obtained for all the alcohols investigated. Since the results are similar only representative data are given here.

The oxidation of secondary alcohols by cerium(IV) results in the formation of the corresponding ketone. Analysis of products and determination of stoichiometry indicate the following overall reaction.

Rate laws: When the concentration of the alcohol is in excess, the disappearance of cerium(IV) follows first order rate law in the individual kinetic run. The pseudo-first order coefficients, however, decrease with an increase in the initial $[Ce^{4+}]$. Similar observations were also recorded earlier^{7,8}. Cerium(IV) in nitric acid solution is known to form dimeric species⁹ and the retardation in rate has been explained on the assumption that the dimeric species is not kinetically active.

The value⁹ of K_a at 303 K in 5 M HNO_3 is 17 ± 2 . In the present case the plot of $1/k_1$ vs $[Ce^{4+}]$ is linear. This indicates¹⁰ that an acyclic complex is formed between cerium(IV) and the alcohol.

At a constant cerium(IV) concentration, a Michaelis-Menten type kinetics was obtained with respect to the alcohol concentration (Fig. 1). The

Fig 1. Michaelis-Menten plot between the inverse of first order rate constant (k_1) and the inverse of alcohol concentration in the oxidation of propan-2-ol.

results suggest that the oxidation proceeds through an intermediate complex of the alcohol and cerium(IV).

The variation of rate of oxidation with the concentration of alcohol at a constant $[Ce^{4+}]$ is given by the expression

$$k_1 = \frac{-d[Ce^{4+}]}{dt[Ce^{4+}]} = \frac{k_s [ROH]}{1/K + [ROH]} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{or } 1/k_1 = \frac{1}{K k_s [ROH]} + \frac{1}{k_s} \quad (6)$$

The values of k_s and K were determined from the plots of $1/k_1$ vs $1/[ROH]$ the various alcohols at different temperature (Fig. 1, Tables 1 and 2). Thermodynamic parameters for the formation of the complex and the activation parameter for its decomposition were calculated.

The activation enthalpies and entropies of the decomposition of the cerium(IV) complexes of the seven secondary alcohols are linearly related ($r=0.9924$). The correlation was tested and found genuine by applying Exner's criterion¹¹. The value of isokinetic temperature obtained by Exner's method is 343 K. Current views do not attach much physical significance to isokinetic temperature¹², but the linear correlation implies that all the alcohols are oxidised by the same mechanism.

It is observed that effects of substituents on the formation constant of Ce^{IV} -alcohol complex is small. This accords with observations recorded earlier in benzyl alcohols-CAN¹³, benzyl alcohols- Ce^{IV} perchlorate¹⁴ and mandelic acids-CAN¹⁵ systems.

Effect of hydrogen ion: The increase in the acidity at constant ionic strength decreases the rate of oxidation. Similar decrease has been recorded earlier¹⁶ in the oxidation of cyclohexanol, propan-2-ol and butan-2-ol by CAN. The authors suggested that the reactive oxidising species is $Ce(OH)^{3+}$ and the retardation in rate can be traced to the following equilibrium.

This implies that Ce^{4+} is much less reactive than $Ce(OH)^{3+}$. The values of K_h calculated in the oxidation of three alcohols¹⁶, however, range from 3.6 to 6.2. In the present investigation also the extent of decrease in the rate, with similar variation in acidity, is different for different alcohols. Thus it seems that the effect of hydrogen ion must be traced to some factor involving the alcohol. The results finds an explanation on the assumption the alcohols are protonated in acid solution and the protonated form is kinetically inactive.

TABLE 1—RATE OF DECOMPOSITION OF ALCOHOL-CAN COMPLEX AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

[HNO₃] = 1.0 M
Alcohol

	10 ⁴ k _s , dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹				ΔH* kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS* J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	ΔG* kJ mol ⁻¹
	298 K	303 K	308 K	313 K			
Propan-2-ol	3.24	5.01	7.40	11.0	63.4	-120	99.2
Butan-2-ol	3.34	5.50	7.95	11.5	62.4	-124	99.3
Pentan-2-ol	3.83	5.67	8.50	12.6	61.5	-126	99.0
Hexan-2-ol	4.00	6.04	8.90	13.2	61.3	-126	98.8
1-Chloropropan-2-ol	0.63	1.17	2.24	4.07	96.3	-5	97.8
1-Methoxypropan-2-ol	1.45	2.40	4.00	6.35	77.1	-62	95.6
3-Methylbutan-2-ol	4.38	6.40	9.60	13.2	57.7	-137	98.5

TABLE 2 - FORMATION CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR ROH-CAN COMPLEX

[H⁺] = 1.0 M

Alcohol	K, mol dm ⁻³				-ΔH kJ mol ⁻¹	-ΔS J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	-ΔG kJ mol ⁻¹
	298 K	303 K	308 K	313 K			
Propan-2-ol	1.62	1.26	0.97	0.78	38.6	114	4.63
Butan-2-ol	2.50	1.97	1.55	1.20	37.6	114	3.63
Pentan-2-ol	2.75	2.09	1.66	1.30	38.9	109	6.42
Hexan-2-ol	2.83	2.20	1.70	1.35	37.8	112	4.42
1-Chloropropan-2-ol	1.06	0.83	0.65	0.51	37.7	121	1.64
1-Methoxypropan-2-ol	1.33	1.00	0.80	0.63	37.9	119	2.44
3-Methylbutan-2-ol	3.02	2.30	1.74	1.35	41.2	100	11.0

Alcohols are known to be proton acceptor and protonation constant for many alcohols has been determined both kinetically and spectrophotometrically¹⁷. If equation (8) is valid, then the observed pseudo-first order constant, k₁ can be expressed as

$$k_1 = k'' / (1 + K_p [H^+]) \quad (9)$$

or $1/k_1 = 1/k'' + K_p [H^+] / k'' \quad (10)$

Here k'' is a constant which includes the total concentration of alcohol.

The value of the protonation constant K_p has been calculated from the slope and intercept of the plot of 1/k₁ vs [H⁺] (Table 3). The values of K_p determined here compare favourably with the values obtained by Wells by spectrophotometric method¹⁷.

TABLE 3—PROTONATION CONSTANT (K_p) OF THE ALCOHOLS

Temp. = 298 K, I = 2.0 M

Alcohol	K _p mol dm ⁻³
Propan-2-ol	0.28
Butan-2-ol	0.30
Pentan-2-ol	0.34
Hexan-2-ol	0.37
1-Chloropropan-2-ol	0.14
1-Methoxypropan-2-ol	0.19
3-Methylbutan-2-ol	0.47

Induced polymerisation of acrylonitrile: In an atmosphere of nitrogen, the oxidation of the secondary alcohols by CAN induce polymerisation of acrylonitrile and a white copious precipitate is formed. In the absence of alcohol, there is no reaction between acrylonitrile and CAN. This confirms that CAN behaves as a one-electron

oxidant and a free radical is generated during the oxidation process.

Kinetic isotope effect: The oxidation of propan-2-ol-α-d by CAN was investigated to ascertain the importance of α-C-H cleavage in the rate-determining process. The rates of oxidation of propan-2-ol and propan-2-ol-α-d, at 0.20 M [Alcohol], 0.004 M [Ce⁴⁺], 1.0 M [H⁺] and temp. 308 K, are 10⁴k₁ = 26.7 and 11.6 sec⁻¹, respectively. Thus the value of primary kinetic isotope effect, k_H/k_D = 2.30 at 308 K. This indicates that α-C-H bond is cleaved in the slow step, and which compares favourably with the k_H/k_D = 1.9 obtained by Littler and Waters¹⁸ in the oxidation of cyclohexanol by cerium(IV) sulphate. This coupled with the fact that k_{OH}/k_{OD} is unity¹⁹, in the oxidation of cyclohexanol, suggest that α-C-H bond-rupture is involved in the rate-determining step.

The low value of the kinetic isotope effect is indicative of a non-symmetrical transition state²⁰. This is consistent with the formation of an intermediate complex and its slow decomposition.

k_s ↓ slow

The rate of decomposition of the complex, k_3 , correlates well with Taft's σ^* substituent constants with low negative reaction constants. The value of ρ^* is -0.67 , -0.59 , -0.50 and -0.42 at 298, 303, 308 and 313 K, respectively. Thus the decomposition of Ce^{IV} -alcohol complex leading to the intermediate free radical involves production of an electron-deficient transition state, albeit a weak one. The value of reaction constant is in accord²¹ with the reaction constants of radical reactions which are generally between -0.5 and -1.5 .

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References

1. W. H. RICHARDSON in "Oxidation in Organic Chemistry", ed. K. W. WIBERG, Academic Press, New York, 1985, Part A, p. 242.
2. M. ARDON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1811.
3. B. SETHURAM and S. S. MUHAMAD, *Acta Chim. Hung.*, 1965, 46, 115, 125.
4. S. S. MUHAMAD and K. V. RAO, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1963, 36, 943, 949.
5. J. SHORTER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 1868.
6. N. S. SRINIVASAN and N. VENKATASUBRAMANIAN, *Tetrahedron*, 1974, 30, 419.
7. G. G. RAO and B. H. RAO, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1972, 59, 461.
8. P. S. SANKHLA and R. N. MEHROTRA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, 35, 891.
9. B. D. BLANSTIN and J. W. GRYDER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 540.
10. P. S. SANKHLA and R. N. MEHROTRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 904; *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, 14, 663.
11. O. EXNER, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1964, 29, 1094.
12. J. E. LEFFLER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, 31, 1535.
13. L. B. YOUNG and W. S. TRAHANOVSKY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 91, 5060.
14. T. R. BALASUBRAMANIAN and N. VENKATASUBRAMANIAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 8, 305.
15. K. K. BANERJI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 573.
16. D. L. MATHUR and G. V. BAKORE, *Z. Naturforsch., Teil B*, 1972, 27, 46; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 48, 363; *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1971, 44, 2600.
17. C. F. WELLS, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1961, 57, 1703, 1719.
18. J. S. LITTLER and W. A. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 2767.
19. J. S. LITTLER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 4135.
20. J. MARCH, "Advanced Organic Chemistry", Academic Press, New York, 1977, p. 399.
21. K. B. WIBERG, "Physical Organic Chemistry", Wiley, New York, 1964, p. 404.